

Syntheses, magnetic and spectral studies of the coordination compounds of polystyrene-anchored dibasic tridentate Schiff base

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Several new polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds of the types [PSCH₂-LMn.3DMF], [PSCH₂-LFeCl₂.2DMF], [PSCH₂-LCo.3DMF], [PSCH₂-LNi.3DMF], [PSCH₂-LCu.DMF], [PSCH₂-LZn.DMF], [PSCH₂-LZr(OH)₂.2DMF], [PSCH₂-LMoO₂.DMF], [PSCH₂-LCd.DMF] and [PSCH₂-LUO₂.DMF] (where, PSCH₂-LH₂ is polystyrene-anchored dibasic tridentate Schiff base obtained from the condensation of 3-formylsalicylic acid and 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole) have been synthesized by the reaction of metal salt/metal coordination compound with PSCH₂-LH₂. The Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} compounds are paramagnetic while Zn^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Mo^{VI}, Cd^{II} and U^{VI} compounds are diamagnetic. The Cu^{II} compound is square-planar, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} compounds are tetrahedral, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Mo^{VI} and U^{VI} compounds are octahedral, and Zr^{IV} compound is pentagonal bipyramidal.

The coordination compound forming ability of 1,2,4-triazoles with various metal ions have been reported¹, but no attempt has been made to study the polystyrene-anchored Schiff bases derived from 1,2,4-triazoles. Only a few Schiff bases have been anchored to polymer supports^{2,3}. The syntheses and characterization of the coordination compounds of polystyrene-anchored Schiff base (PSCH₂-LH₂) (1) with Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Zr^{IV}, Mo^{VI}, Cd^{II} and U^{VI} are described here.

Results and discussion

The polystyrene-anchored Schiff base (PSCH₂-LH₂) (1), was obtained by the reaction of PSCH₂-Cl and LH₂ in 1 : 3 molar ratio. If the above ratio is kept 1 : <3, the polystyrene-anchored Schiff base obtained always contains some unreacted chlorine. IR spectral data and the elemental analyses suggest 100% conversion of PSCH₂-Cl to PSCH₂-LH₂ (1). As the reaction progresses, the white colour of PSCH₂-Cl changes to yellow. The yellow colour of PSCH₂-LH₂ (1) remains unaffected even after several washings with DMF, ethyl acetate, methanol, ethanol and acetone. The reaction of metal salt/metal acetate with PSCH₂-LH₂ in 1 : 2 ratio yields the polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds. The conversion of PSCH₂-LH₂ was always found

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds

Compd. ^a	Colour	Metal% : Found (Calcd.)	Metal-binding capacity ^b × 10 ⁻² mmol/g of resin	Conversion ^c %
[PSCH ₂ -LMn.3DMF]	Dark brown	3.07 (3.10)	56.4	89.1
[PSCH ₂ -LFeCl ₂ .2DMF]	Reddish brown	1.41 (1.43)	25.1	39.0
[PSCH ₂ -LCo.3DMF]	Brown	2.84 (2.85)	47.5	75.3
[PSCH ₂ -LNi.3DMF]	Yellowish green	2.15 (1.17)	20.4	32.3
[PSCH ₂ -LCu.DMF]	Brown	3.12 (3.16)	48.8	70.3
[PSCH ₂ -LZn.DMF]	Light yellow	3.07 (3.08)	47.4	68.4
[PSCH ₂ -LZr(OH) ₂ .2DMF]	Cream	3.72 (3.76)	40.6	63.9
[PSCH ₂ -LMoO ₂ .DMF]	Yellow	4.15 (4.18)	43.8	65.9
[PSCH ₂ -LCd.DMF]	Yellow	3.80 (3.83)	33.8	50.3
[PSCH ₂ -LUO ₂ .DMF]	Orange	10.31 (10.36)	43.3	71.3

^aAbbreviation : PSCH₂-LH₂ = 1, DMF = dimethylformamide.

^bMetal binding capacity = [M% (observed) × 10]/(atomic weight of metal).

^cPercentage reaction conversion (P) = (observed metal ion percentage × 100)/(calculated metal ion percentage on the basis of 100% reaction conversion of polystyrene-anchored ligand to polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds.

to be <100% and was in the range 32.3–89.1 (Table 1). The metal binding capacity of PSCH₂-LH₂ varies from 20.4 × 10⁻² to 56.4 × 10⁻² mmol of metal per g of PSCH₂-LH₂ (Table 1). PSCH₂-Cl with less chlorine content (0.94 mmol of Cl per g of PSCH₂-Cl) was used to avoid the formation of magnetically concentrated polymer bound coordination compounds.

The infrared spectral data of PSCH₂-LH₂ and its metal coordination compounds were recorded in KBr. PSCH₂-LH₂ exhibits ν_{C=N} (azomethine) and ν_{C-O} (phenolic) stretches at 1610 and 1545 cm⁻¹, respectively⁴. The presence of a medium intense band around 3200 cm⁻¹ (N-H) and absence of a ν_{SH} band⁵ around 2500 cm⁻¹ indicate thione form of the ligand. The band at 1120 cm⁻¹ (C=S) was observed in polystyrene-anchored ligand⁶. A shift of ν_{C=N} (azomethine) to lower energy by 10–30 cm⁻¹ in the polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds indicates that coordination takes place through nitrogen atom⁴. The ν_{C-O} (phenolic) band in polystyrene-anchored compounds shifted to higher energy by ≤10 cm⁻¹, which indicates the coordination of the phenolic oxygen atom⁴. The disappearance of ν_{C-S} band in the polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds and the appearance of a new band at 680–695 cm⁻¹ (C-S) indicate the thione ⇌ thiol tautomerism followed by deprotonation of thiol group and consequent coordination of sulfur atom^{5,6}. Thus PSCH₂-LH₂ behaves as tridentate ONS donors dibasic ligand.

In [PSCH₂-LFeCl₂.2DMF], the absence of a band at 820–840 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{asy} (Fe–O–Fe) precludes the formation of an oxo-bridged structure⁷. In the polystyrene-anchored zirconium(IV) compound, the absence of a band at 850–950 cm⁻¹ (Zr=O)⁸ favours the formulation of [PSCH₂-LZr(OH)₂.2DMF] and not [PSCH₂-LZrO(H₂O).2DMF]. The appearance of a new band at 1130 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to the δ_{Zr-OH}⁸. [PSCH₂-LMoO₂.DMF] possesses the *cis*-MoO₂ moiety, as confirmed by the presence of ν_{sym} (O=Mo=O) and ν_{asym} (O=Mo=O) at 930 and 900 cm⁻¹, respectively. These bands lie in the usual ranges observed for the majority of *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(VI) compounds⁹. The absence of a band around 770 cm⁻¹ in the present compound suggests the absence of an oligomeric chain structure with ...Mo=O...Mo=O... interaction⁹. [PSCH₂-LUO₂.DMF] showed a band at 915 cm⁻¹ due to the ν_{asym} (O=U=O) and this band lies in the usual range (870–950 cm⁻¹) observed for the majority of U^{VI} compounds¹⁰. The appearance of the ν_{asym} (O=U=O) band is indicative of *trans*-UO₂ moiety. The force constant (f_{U-O}) calculated according to the method¹¹, is 6.96 mdyne/Å and lies within the expected range (6.58–7.03 mdyne/Å) reported for the majority of dioxouranium(VI) compounds^{10,11}. The U–O bond length (R) calculated by using the equation¹²: R = 1.08 f^{-1/3} + 1.17, is 1.74 Å and lies in the expected range

(1.60–1.92 Å). DMF exhibits a band due to ν(C=O) stretch¹³ at 1680 cm⁻¹, which shifted to lower energy by 15–50 cm⁻¹ in the polystyrene-anchored compounds, suggesting oxygen coordination of DMF. The IR data of PSCH₂-LH₂ and its coordination compounds are comparable in the non-anchored ligand and its coordination compounds⁴.

The reflectance spectrum of [PSCH₂-LMn.3DMF] exhibited two bands at 17100 and 25450 cm⁻¹ due to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(G) transitions, respectively, in an octahedral symmetry¹⁴. [PSCH₂-LFeCl₂.2DMF] showed three bands at 11900, 18550 and 25000 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(G), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(G) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴A_{1g}(G), respectively, in an octahedral symmetry¹⁵. [PSCH₂-LCo.3DMF] showed two bands at 8995 and 20300 cm⁻¹ due to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(v₁) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P)(v₃) transitions, respectively, in an octahedral symmetry¹⁵. The v₃/v₁ value is 2.13 and lies in the usual range (2.0–2.80) reported for the majority of Co^{II} octahedral coordination compounds¹⁵. The reflectance spectral parameters of the present compounds are: Dq = 1002 cm⁻¹, B' = 748 cm⁻¹, β = 0.77 and β⁰ = 23%. The reduction of Racah parameter from the free ion value of 971 to 748 cm⁻¹ and β⁰ value of 23% indicate the covalent nature of [PSCH₂-LCo.3DMF]. The three bands observed at 8990, 16090 and 25200 cm⁻¹ in [PSCH₂-LNi.3DMF] may be assigned to the spin-allowed transitions ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g}(v₁), ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(p)(v₂) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g}(F)(v₃), respectively in an octahedral symmetry¹⁵. The observed v₂/v₁ value of 1.79 lies in the range (1.6–1.82) reported for the majority of octahedral Ni^{II} coordination compounds. The spectral parameters for the present compounds are: Dq = 899 cm⁻¹, B' = 865 cm⁻¹, β = 0.82 and β⁰ = 18%. The reduction of Racah parameter from the free ion value of 1056 to 865 cm⁻¹ and β⁰ value of 18% are indicative of covalent nature of the present compound. [PSCH₂-LCu.DMF] showed one broad band at 18450 cm⁻¹ characteristic of square-planar geometry¹⁶. The absence of a band in the region (8000–10000 cm⁻¹) precludes the presence of a tetrahedral structure¹⁷.

The polystyrene-anchored Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} coordination compounds exhibit magnetic moments of 5.89, 6.01, 4.89, 3.17 and 2.10 B.M., respectively. These data are close to the reported values¹⁸: ~5.9 B.M. for Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} compounds; 4.7–5.2 B.M. for Co^{II} compounds; 2.9–3.4 B.M. for Ni^{II} compounds, and 1.75–2.20 B.M. for Cu^{II} compounds. The polystyrene-anchored coordination compounds of Zr^{IV}, Mo^{VI}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and U^{VI} are diamagnetic as expected for d⁰, d¹⁰ or f⁰ systems.

The ESR spectrum of [PSCH₂-LCu.DMF] has been recorded in polycrystalline solid in the absence of a host diamagnetic diluent. The g_{||} and g_⊥ values are 2.23 and 2.07, respectively. The higher value of g_{||} in comparison to g_⊥,

suggests the presence of unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The two g values also indicate the presence of a tetragonal symmetry around the Cu^{II} ions¹⁹. The presence of a large ligand framework keeps the metal centres considerably separated avoiding any dipolar broadening. It has been shown (see below) that the metal ions are situated on a phenyl ring (of chloromethylated polystyrene) which are situated eight to nine styrene units apart and this leads to a magnetically dilute environment around the metal ions since the Cu–Cu interaction is blocked.

General method of calculation showing the presence of metal ions situated on phenyl ring at eight to nine styrene units apart : Chloromethylated polystyrene (0.94 mmol of Cl per g of resin) has the following structure :

($\text{PSCH}_2\text{-Cl}$)

where x is an integer or a fractional number. Assuming chloromethylated polystyrene to contain A equivalents of CH_2Cl and B equivalents of styrene unit per g of resin, then

$$A \times 152.5 + B \times 104 = 1 \text{ g}$$

where 152.5 and 104 are the molecular weights of chloromethylated polystyrene and styrene respectively, Hence,

$$B : A = \frac{1 - 152.5 A}{104 A} : 1$$

$$B : A = x : 1, \text{ where } x = \frac{1 - 152.5 A}{104 A}$$

$$\text{or } x = \frac{1 - 152.5 \times 0.00094}{104 \times 0.00094}$$

$$\text{or } x = 8.76$$

Experimental

4-Amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole, 3-formylsalicylic acid, zirconium(IV) acetate and bis(acetylacetonato)-dioxomolybdenum(VI) were synthesized according to the published procedures²⁰. Chloromethylated polystyrene ($\text{PSCH}_2\text{-Cl}$) (0.94 mmol of Cl per g of resin and 1% crosslinked with divinylbenzene) (Sigma), manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate (Sarabhai M. Chemicals), ferric chloride (anhydrous), cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate, cadmium(II) acetate tetrahydrate, dioxouranium(VI) acetate tetrahydrate (B.D.H.), nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (Fluka), zinc(II) acetate dihydrate (S.D.'s Fine chemicals), copper(II) acetate monohydrate, petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (Indian Drugs and Pharmaceuticals Ltd.), acetone, methanol, DMF, triethylamine and ethyl acetate (Ranbaxy) were used for syntheses.

The Mn^{II} contents of [$\text{PSCH}_2\text{-LMn.3DMF}$] were determined by leaching the compound with hot 6 *N* CH_3COOH followed by filtering off the polymer and washing with distilled water. The leached Mn^{II} ions were estimated complexometrically with EDTA using eriochrome black-T as indicator. The metal contents in the remaining polystyrene-anchored compounds were determined according to reported procedure²¹. The coordinated DMF was determined by heating the polystyrene-anchored compounds at 160–180° for 3 h. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as a calibrant and the diamagnetic corrections were computed using the reported procedure³. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet FTIR spectrophotometer and reflectance spectra on a Beckmann DU spectrophotometer. ESR spectrum was recorded at room temperature in polycrystalline solid on a Varian V4502–12 X-band spectrometer (100 kHz). The g values were calculated as per the literature method²².

Schiff base [5-mercapto-3-methyl-4-(3-carboxysalicylidineamino)-1,2,4-triazole] (LH_2) : An ethanolic solution (30 ml) of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole (1.30 g, 10 mmol) was added while stirring to an ethanolic solution (30 ml) of 3-formylsalicylic acid (1.66 g, 10 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 1 h in presence of a few drops of piperidine. The solvent was then partially evaporated and the yellow crystalline product obtained was dried under vacuum, (70%), m.p. 200° (Found : N, 19.3; S, 10.8. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3\text{N}_4\text{S}$ calcd. for : N, 20.14, S, 11.51%); ν_{max} 1650 (C=N azomethine), 1545 (C–O phenolic) and 1115 cm^{-1} (C=S).

Polystyrene-anchored Schiff base ($\text{PSCH}_2\text{-LH}_2$) (1) : $\text{PSCH}_2\text{-Cl}$ (1.0 g) was allowed to swell in DMF (20 ml) for 45 min. The Schiff base (0.78 g, 2.82 mmol) was dissolved in DMF (30 ml) and added to the above suspension. Ethyl acetate (100 ml) and triethylamine (3 ml) were then added to the mixture while stirring magnetically and the mixture was refluxed for 8 h. The resulting yellow solid was washed several times with DMF, ethyl acetate, methanol and ethanol, and dried under vacuum : ν_{max} 1610 (C=N azomethine), 1545 (C–O phenolic) and 1120 cm^{-1} (C=S thiocarbonyl).

[$\text{PSCH}_2\text{-LZr}(\text{OH})_2.2\text{DMF}$] : The polystyrene-anchored Schiff base (1; 0.5 g, 0.47 mmol) was allowed to swell in DMF (20 ml) for 1 h. To it a DMF solution (40 ml) of freshly prepared zirconium(IV) acetate (1.01 g, 0.94 mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 6 h while stirring magnetically. The cream coloured polystyrene-anchored compound obtained was washed several times the DMF, methanol, ethanol and acetone and dried under vacuum at room temperature.

Other coordination compounds of PSCH₂-LH₂ : The polystyrene-anchored Schiff base (**1**; 0.5 g, 0.47 mmol) was allowed to swell in DMF (20 ml) for 1 h. To it a DMF solution (30–50 ml) of the appropriate metal acetate/metal chloride/MoO₂(acac)₂ (0.94 mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 8 h while stirring magnetically using CaCl₂ guard tube. In the synthesis of [PSCH₂-LCo.3DMF], the reaction was carried out in N₂ atmosphere. The polystyrene-anchored compounds were washed several times with DMF, methanol, ethanol and acetone and dried under vacuum at room temperature.

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